

TANGENT back-end service for real-time traffic forecasting

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Abstract: Accurate traffic prediction is essential for enhancing intelligent transportation systems, enabling better route planning, congestion mitigation, and dynamic traffic management, which collectively contribute to environmental sustainability. While existing research predominantly leverages historical data for model development, there is a notable gap in real-time implementation for practical applications. This paper presents a novel approach for deploying real-time traffic forecasting models within the TANGENT H2020 project, focusing on three cities: Greater Manchester, Lisbon, and Rennes. Utilizing diverse data sources such as loop detectors and Waze trajectories, our methodology encompasses a comprehensive nine-step framework. Central to our approach is the use of the Multivariate time series forecasting with graph neural networks (MTGNN) for deep learning-based predictions, optimized and deployed via the Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) format. Integration with RabbitMQ for data brokering and Nvidia’s Triton Inference Server ensures efficient real-time processing and scalability. The system successfully delivers traffic predictions with sub-second latency. Results integrated into the TANGENT dashboard showcase the system’s capability to provide timely and accurate traffic insights. This work underscores the feasibility and effectiveness of deploying advanced deep learning models in real-time settings.

1 INTRODUCTION

Traffic prediction plays a crucial role in intelligent transportation systems, facilitating improved route planning, congestion reduction, and dynamic traffic management. Such advancements contribute significantly to environmental sustainability by minimizing time and energy lost due to traffic congestion. While much of the existing research relies on historical data for model training and testing, few studies have effectively implemented their models in real-time settings for real-world applications. In this study, we introduce our approach to deploying trained traffic forecasting models in real-time.

The TANGENT H2020 project is improving the management of mobility flows, e.g. in terms of monitoring and forecasting tools. It enables the implementation and integration of innovative mobility solutions to contribute to more efficient traffic management. This paper describes a solution to provide traf-

fic predictions for three cities represented in the TANGENT project, namely Greater Manchester, Lisbon, and Rennes. Different data sources are considered for the different case studies, ranging from traffic speed and count for loop detectors up to Waze trajectories.

The proposed solution in this work consists of 9 steps, which are explained in more depth in the methodology section. We then highlight some results from the proposed framework in the results section and finally conclude the paper in the conclusion section.

2 METHODOLOGY

The focus of this work is on the back-end integration of supply forecasting. The supply side of a transport network can be defined by traffic measurements such as traffic speed, travel time, and flow. Data-driven approaches have shown excellent results with the rise of data collection and computational resources. This implemented method for traffic supply forecasting within the TANGENT project is described in Figure 1. The steps for the supply forecasting process are

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described below:

1. Collection of historical and real-time traffic data. Historical data (e.g., time series of flows, speeds) coming from available traffic counters, floating vehicle data, etc., should preferably represent one year worth of data to incorporate all seasonal effects and is used for the training of the deep learning model. Real-time data, with a similar format, is used to provide traffic supply predictions in real-time based on the trained model.
2. Deep learning modelling that performs predictions on these types of input data. For each dataset in each case study, we optimize the model's hyperparameters on the validation set to get the best results. The base architecture used is MTGNN (Wu et al., 2020). It is one of the state-of-the-art models in deep learning. The method uses graph learning layer, Graph Convolutional Networks and Temporal CNNs to capture latent dependencies in spatial and temporal contexts.

The output of these models are time series predictions for the future time steps. The model uses windows of past and current traffic values as input and returns windows of future traffic values as output. The standard practice is to use the same window size as input and output. A two hour prediction where the data is sampled every 15 minutes is a window of size 8. The adjacency matrix represents the spatial relation which the model uses to combine each location's past values with its neighbors.

The proposed solution for the deployment of real-time traffic forecasting is presented in Figure 2. It consists of 9 steps, which are detailed below.

In the first step, the MTGNN model is trained by historical data provided by partners within the TANGENT project. Traffic speed and flow from loop detectors is used for the Manchester case study, and Traffic speed and segment travel time from Waze is used for the Rennes case study. The models are trained using PyTorch (Paszke et al., 2017).

The next step of the process begins with the conversion of trained deep learning models into Open Neural Network Exchange ONNX format (ONNX, 2024). ONNX provides interoperability among various AI tools and frameworks which enables seamless deployment on different platforms and with different engines that support the ONNX standard. It also enables a reliable way of deploying models on various systems because of framework agnosticism, standardization, broad support from industry, and performance optimizations it does for the model. The conversion is done using export tools provided by PyTorch.

After exporting the models, we developed a system that connects to a RabbitMQ (RabbitMQ, 2024)

data broker provided by the TANGENT dashboard (Dias et al., 2023). RabbitMQ is one the most popular open-source brokers that implements the Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) standard. We use the pika python library to communicate with RabbitMQ. Pika offers an interface to establish connections, declare exchanges, queues and handle message delivery.

After the establishment of the connection with the data broker, the system continuously listens for incoming traffic data such as speed and flow through the established AMQP channels. The data is filtered for each city and data source. When enough data is gathered (e.g., 12 time steps of 5 minutes when the required input is 1 hour), locations outside of the study area are removed and the missing values are filled with zeros. The models are trained using masked losses to handle missing values represented as zeros.

The data is then normalized using the same statistics as the training data. Normalizing data is a standard procedure in many deep learning applications. Then those traffic values are combined (like speed and flow) in a NumPy array suitable for the deep learning model input.

Once enough data is collected and processed, the system composes an inference request and sends it to the Triton Inference Server using gRPC (gRPC, 2024). gRPC is an open-source universal Remote Procedure Call framework to connect services within data centers with the support of load balancing, tracing, health checking and authentication. Triton, developed by Nvidia, supports ONNX models and provides a robust platform for deploying, serving, and scaling deep learning inference models.

After processing the inference request, the Triton server sends back the prediction results. This includes traffic speed, traffic count, and segment travel times depending on the case study and data availability. The response is received by the system using the same gRPC framework used for sending the request.

Upon receiving the predictions, the system performs several post-processing steps. First, the data is denormalized using training data statistics, then the timestamps are calculated for each prediction and the data is transformed to the correct format required by the data provider to use in the Tangent dashboard.

Finally, the processed traffic predictions are pushed to the stakeholders providing the Tangent dashboard using the same AMQP setup.

Figure 1: Deep Learning Forecasting Framework used in this study

Figure 2: The proposed framework for real-time traffic forecasting back-end within the TANGENT project

3 RESULTS

The results of traffic forecasting are added to the TANGENT dashboard where the current status of the network is shown in addition to traffic forecasts. Figure 3 illustrates this dashboard layout.

Additionally, a sample of 1-hour predictions is depicted in Figure 4. These charts are used for testing purposes, while the predictions are incorporated in the TANGENT dashboard. There, each location prediction is depicted on the map of the study area.

The prediction is done on 233 segments in Manchester and 78 segments in Rennes. The preprocessing, inference, and postprocessing duration for Manchester traffic speed and flow predictions are around 170 and 160 milliseconds, respectively. It also takes around 20 milliseconds to publish the predictions for both speed and flow. For the Rennes case study, the preprocessing for both traffic speed and travel time takes less than 200 milliseconds, and the inference time and post-processing take about 35 milliseconds for each of them. Publishing predictions takes about 10 milliseconds for both speed and travel time. This system efficiently integrates data collection, processing, and state-of-the-art prediction of up to two hours, all within less than a second, showcasing high execution performance.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The proposed system represents a comprehensive approach for the deployment of real-time traffic prediction, applied to 3 case studies within the TANGENT project. The results shown in this work are provided for the case studies of Greater Manchester and Rennes for road traffic, while completed work on the Lisbon case study and public transport in Rennes is not included here. The proposed approach uses state-of-the-art technologies and protocols to ensure high performance, scalability, and reliability. The use of ONNX for model format, AMQP for reliable messaging, and Triton Inference Server for efficient model inferencing ensures a fast, real-time, and reliable system.

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Figure 3: Forecasting results within the dashboard interface for the city of Rennes.

(a) 5-minute predictions

(b) 60-minute predictions

Figure 4: Traffic count forecasting results for Manchester case study at different intervals using a loop detector located on Oldham Rd. The red lines represent the predicted value and the green lines indicate the actual observed data.

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